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KRISSELLE DONNA A. BALETBET

Assistant Professor II

Apayao State College

kriselledonnaaquilana@gmail.com

“THE QUIET TRIUMPH OF CONTENTMENT”

Are we meant to always keep moving,
chasing horizons yet unseen?

Are we bound to endless proving,
to become more than we have been?

But what if peace has found my heart,
and stillness feels enough for me?

Must I run just to play my part
in someone else's race to be?

They measure lives beside your own,
with scales that only they define;
yet every path is not the same—
success can wear a different sign.

They think they stand a step ahead,
they claim their joy is bright and true;
but what their hurried eyes have missed
is the calm that lives in you.

For in a world that rushes fast,
where endless striving fills the air,
there lies a victory soft and vast—
the quiet triumph of contentment.